

Basketball Training is an Effective Physical Education Tool

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Abstract: This article examines the characteristics of the sports game of basketball as a means of physical education. Also, regular basketball training helps to develop in students perseverance, courage, confidence, determination, self-confidence and a sense of collectivism. The relevance and effectiveness of education depend on the purposefulness of the relationship between physical and moral education in the pedagogical process.

Keywords: basketball, efficiency, physical education, training, process, physical training, student, formation, physical exercises, physical qualities.

Introduction

The current problem of the modern sports training system is the need to obtain urgent information about the preparedness of basketball players in order to manage the training process. The relevance of basketball as a means of physical education has found widespread application in various levels of physical activity. It is characterized by a variety of movements: walking, running, stopping, turning, jumping, catching, throwing and carrying the ball, which are carried out in a duel with opponents. Such diverse movements contribute to improving metabolism, the functioning of all the body's systems, and form coordination.

Basketball, as an important means of physical education and health of children, is included in the general education programs of secondary schools, polytechnic and industrial schools, children's sports schools, city departments of public education and sports volunteer societies. To study the readiness of young basketball players to overcome the resistance of opposing defenders, a program for testing the readiness of basketball players was developed. In the process of developing this program, the principle was followed, where the studied indicators were determined by factors that are significant for young basketball players and arise in the conditions of opponents. Factors determining basketball players' readiness for game and competition activities included: distance; opponents' performance; defender's high level of activity; defender's physical fitness; players' fouls when throwing the ball; the attacker's position relative to the defender.

The diversity of technical and tactical actions in the game of basketball and the game itself has unique properties for the formation of vital skills and abilities, comprehensive physical and mental development. The mastered motor actions of basketball and related physical exercises are effective means of strengthening health and can be used by a person throughout his life in independent forms of physical education.

Long-term education of children requires taking into account the peculiarities of their age

development, and in this regard, a careful selection of means and methods of educational work. Currently, there are many manuals that comprehensively cover modern basketball techniques. In them, general issues of organizing pedagogical work are presented, as well as specific practical materials that need to be mastered at a certain age.

For basketball, not only height, but also weight, hand diameter measurements/longitudinal, transverse/, and the distance between the extended fingers are important, which, due to the hand-ball ratio, are undoubtedly important for performing a number of technical elements. The great wrist, the long moving and flexible fingers give the player a great advantage in possession of the ball.

If for a university lecturer, when selecting students for basketball sports improvement groups, the morphological features, physical and functional qualities, and personality traits are important, then the former occupies a significant portion of the total.

The student's significant height/close to two meters/, a large wrist diameter, a small fat layer, a large length of the legs and arms are preferable when selecting for basketball games, in the groups of basketball sports improvement.

Having a choice of first-year students with average morphological data, the university teacher has to pay more attention to the special physical qualities of students.

The first year students are mainly 17-18 years old. Therefore, an average of 45% of them (men) have a harmonious body type. So, we have to choose a basketball specialization, mainly students with average shoulder width and leg length, and a very small percentage of students with a hygienic body type, a large shoulder width and leg length.

The speed and accuracy of operational thinking play an important role in a basketball player's game activity, the speed of technical and tactical elements, while it is necessary to consider the speed of mental operations that contribute to the rapidly changing situation of opponents' actions in the game. An operational assessment of the game situation, taking into account its further development, allows the basketball player to realistically assess the situation and determine the optimal choice of the offensive method or throwing method.

In modern basketball, to achieve high sports results, it is necessary to use large training loads. In sports practice, coaches do not have a single opinion on what training tools and how much to use in classes, what the duration of work should be, what the rest intervals in the series and between them should be. In this regard, the issue of controlling training loads and taking into account their impact on the athlete's body is relevant.

To obtain rapid information about the basketball player's condition, an operational control of training loads was used, which evaluates the player's condition before and after completing one exercise, a series of exercises, and a whole session.

In basketball sports, a key technique is the passing of the ball, which allows the player to direct the ball to the partner to continue the attack.

The ability to pass the ball accurately and on time is the basis of clear, purposeful interaction in the game. There are many different ways of passing the ball. They are used depending on a particular game situation, the distance from which the ball should be sent, the position or direction of the opponents.

The speed and accuracy of the transfers largely depend on the correct, energetic work of the hands and fingers in the main phase of receiving. Therefore, special attention should be paid to these details when planning training work to improve the transfer technique.

It should be remembered that the partner who receives the ball must be seen, but not directly looked at him. One important methodological rule must be observed in the transmission, namely the maintenance of balance, since the direction of the intended transmission may be obstructed by the

opponent. In this regard, the attacker can make a "run" or allow the ball to be intercepted. In this case, a well-thought-out pass can be intercepted by the defender. It is clear that part of the wrong action can be attributed to the partner who receives the ball, but the main responsibility for the loss of the ball is always borne by the passer.

The choice of content, forms, methods, techniques and means of learning is carried out taking into account the age-sex, morpho-functional characteristics and individual capabilities of students. Priority skills, which are formed in the process of basketball training, complement and improve practically all physical qualities necessary for the full and harmonious development of engaged children.

Only a systematic approach can achieve high productivity. The main sections of the system provide for in-depth study of basketball. The knowledge and skills acquired by students in the field of basketball in physical culture classes are improved, special motor skills are brought to automation in conditions close to competitive ones.

Conclusion

Therefore, it can be concluded that using this model demonstrated a stable interest in basketball among students, which in turn is aimed at developing a need for a healthy lifestyle, fostering negative attitudes towards harmful habits. The constant growth and dynamic development of motor qualities allows for competition in game activities, teaches sportsmanship, allows for the experience of sports enthusiasm and a sense of victory in the event of luck and a fighting spirit in the event of defeat.

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